

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL-PRACTICAL COMPETENCE OF WOMEN AND GIRLS ON THE BASIS OF HANDICRAFTS

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Abstract. *Consideration of the role of personality activity in development professional competencies are logically connected with highlighting the concept of excess activity. The degree of human activity in shaping one's own destiny is largely determined by the ability to set goals for oneself, worthy of a person and allowing him to go beyond the limits of his current capabilities. By excess professional activity we will understand activity expressed in the individual's desire to exceed the requirements of normatively approved professional activity and job responsibilities.*

Keywords: *cognitive activity, immediate analysis and immediate action, pedagogical perception, pedagogical innovation.*

Study of professional competence teacher makes it necessary to highlight its structural components, as well as descriptions of their content. Specifics of professional competence teachers is determined by the characteristics of the pedagogical labor, its differences from other types of activity.

Several differences can be identified:

1. Operational and systematic nature requires pedagogical work, according to A.S. Makarenko, "immediate analysis and immediate action" [4].
2. Limited options for reliable choice the best solution to a problem situation.
3. Pedagogical work is carried out constantly, day after day, but its results do not appear immediately, the property of "remote" effectiveness is manifested.
4. Essential professional feature teacher's job is the ability to predict further opportunities for developing the qualities of students according to the primary results of exposure.
5. Each teacher works individually, but simultaneously, the results of training and education consist of the collective efforts of different teachers. Often there is a lack of unity of requirements in pedagogical team can significantly reduce the efficiency the work of individual teachers.
6. Effective pedagogical process determined by the integrity of the efforts of each of his participants (teachers, students and their parents, administration).
7. The work of a teacher is internally contradictory, in it combines specialized knowledge, skills and abilities (for individual disciplines, branches of science and production) and general professional psychological and pedagogical knowledge, skills and abilities. In addition, such internal heterogeneity of the teaching profession makes it significantly difficult to compare the level professional competence for different groups teachers, especially demanding a differentiated approach [5, p. 29-31].

The decisive influence on the structure of professional competence in accordance with its goals in the professional training system is exerted by:

- structure of cognitive activity;

- structure of the total object of study –the reality surrounding a person, reflected in subject structure of scientific knowledge;
- the need and specificity of specific types cognitive activity;
- the need to develop positive individual personality traits (abilities, interests, inclinations);
- logic of development of the main parallels of educational process [6].

Structure of professional competence V.A. Slastenin proposes to reveal through the totality general and specific professional skills. Ideally full compliance of the specialist with the requirements qualification characteristics means the formation of an integrated whole set of professional skills.

In the work of N.E. Kostyleva presents the following components of teacher professional competence:

- personal-humanistic orientation;
- pedagogical perception;
- pedagogical skills;
- pedagogical creativity.

They are connected and form an integral system, based on which the author defines professional teacher competence as a complex individual psychological education, which is based on integration of experience, theoretical knowledge, practical skills and significant personal qualities, conditioning the teacher's readiness for actual embodiment of pedagogical activity [6].

E.G. Islamgaliev indicates that it is productive identifying three components of professional competence: professional knowledge, communication and self-improvement. Similarly, the distinction two groups of indicators - procedural (three sides teacher's work: teaching activities, pedagogical communication, personality) and effective (training and learning ability, good manners and students' educational performance) [11]. This implies "human-centric" emphasis when determining the level professional competence.

The acquisition of knowledge is not an end in itself, but a necessary condition for the development of "knowledge in action", that is, skills and abilities - the main criterion of professional readiness. In the most general form, psychological and pedagogical knowledge is determined by educational programs. Psychological, pedagogical and special (subject) knowledge is necessary, but far from a sufficient condition for professional competence.

Many of them, in particular theoretical, practical and methodological knowledge is a prerequisite pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skills is a set of sequentially unfolding external or internal plan of pedagogical actions, some of which can be automated (skills), aimed at solving the problems of developing a harmonious personality and based on relevant theoretical knowledge. As a result, the model of professional teacher competence can be represented as the unity of its theoretical and practical readiness. On based on these approaches, pedagogical skills are combined into four groups:

- constructive – the ability to set pedagogical tasks. They are related to the "translation" of content objective process of socialization into specific tasks training and education: studying the individual and the team with the purpose of determining the level of readiness for active mastering new knowledge and designing on this the basis of the development of the team and individual students;

- identifying a complex of educational, educational and developing tasks, their specification and definition dominant task;

- organizational – ability to program a method pedagogical action. They allow you to build and set in motion a logically complete pedagogical system: comprehensive planning educational, educational and developmental tasks; reasonable selection of educational content process; optimal choice of forms, methods and means of its organizations;

- communicative – the ability to perform a pedagogical action. They involve identifying and establishing the relationship between the components and factors of education and training, putting them into action: creating the necessary conditions (material, moral-psychological, organizational, hygienic, etc.) for the implementation of the educational process; development of student activities,

transforming it from an object into a subject of pedagogical process; organization and development of joint activities; ensuring the connection between the school and the environment, regulating external non-programmable impacts;

- Gnostic – the ability to study the results of solving a problem. They require taking into account and evaluating the results of teaching activities: self-analysis and analysis of the progress of the pedagogical process and the actions of the teacher; defining a new set of dominant and subordinate pedagogical tasks.

Pedagogical competence will only be a set of professional skills if it is not infused with pedagogical creativity. Without co-creation with students, a productive process is unthinkable. In this regard, the approach to co-creation is interesting - highlighting a number of levels of co-creation:

- level of elementary interaction with the class:

the teacher uses feedback, adjusts his influences based on its results, but he acts “according to manual”, “based on a template”, based on the experience of other teachers;

- level of optimization of activities in the lesson, starting with its planning, when creativity comes into play in skillful selection and appropriate combination of content, methods and forms of teaching already known to the teacher;

- heuristic, when the teacher uses the creative possibilities of live communication with students;

- the highest level of co-creation of the teacher, which is characterized by his complete independence, with using ready-made techniques he invests in them personal beginning, so they correspond to it creative individuality, personality traits pupil, the specific level of development of the class [9, p.35-36].

The author also considers the issue of the relationship concepts “pedagogical skill”, “pedagogical skill”, "pedagogical innovation" and "professional competence".

The next stage of professional growth and teacher improvement is pedagogical excellence. Pedagogical skill is nothing more than as brought to a high degree of perfection teaching and educational skills that reflect special polished methods and techniques of application psychological and pedagogical theory in practice, thanks to which ensures high efficiency of the educational process.

The highest level of professional activity teachers is pedagogical innovation.

Pedagogical innovation organically includes promotion and implementation of new, progressive ideas, principles and techniques in the process of training and education and a very significant increase in their quality.

According to the author, frequently used categories “pedagogical skill”, “pedagogical skill”, “pedagogical creativity” are not so much single-row, how many can act as quality characteristics of teachers' qualification levels.

During the study, the author set the task determine in what ratio they are professional competence, pedagogical mastery and pedagogical creativity and develop the most complete indicators of these connections.

So, pedagogical skill is an activity teacher at the level of samples and standards worked out in practice and already described in methodological developments and recommendations. The skill of a teacher is not directly related to his work experience. Unlike skill pedagogical creativity is always a search and finding something new: either for yourself (discovering teacher of variable non-standard solutions pedagogical tasks), or for oneself and for others (creation new original approaches to individual techniques, reconstructing known pedagogical experience).

Mastery – high degree of mastery a certain type of specialized activity, is based on a deep understanding of the matter, combined with developed skills to carry out rational and effective actions. Creativity, creative activity - activity that generates something qualitatively new and unique, originality and socio-historical uniqueness. Thus, we can conclude that mastery is part of pedagogical creativity and is a component of professional competence.

The development of pedagogical stagnation depends on teacher centering. Least stagnation observed among teachers of humanistic and cognitive (methodological) centering. Stagnation also contributes to the fact that the teacher conveys experience: knowledge, skills, skills that have already become property of society, annually teaches a certain educational material according to a relatively stable program, uses the same teaching technologies. Pedagogical creativity in itself is a process that begins with the assimilation of what has already been accumulated (adaptation, reproduction, reproduction knowledge and experience), to change, transformation existing experience. The path from adaptation to pedagogical situation before its transformation is the essence of the dynamics of teacher creativity.

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